

TOWARDS EVIDENCE BASED ENTREPRENEURSHIP: EXPLORING THE CRITICAL FACTORS OF THE LEAN STARTUP METHODOLOGY FOR NEW VENTURE DEVELOPMENT

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Despite the increased role and relevance of new venture development in knowledge based economies, most start-ups fail within a short period. High start-up failure rates are regarded as major issue in developed economies. The Lean Start-up Methodology proposes a fundamentally different approach from the traditional business planning; an evidence based method for building businesses. The aim of this study is to provide empirical evidence and draw practical implications by exploring the critical areas of the concept drawn from the debate on the subject; the confusion and uncertainty related to the concept, the concerns of quality and funding associated issues. This inquiry based on interviews with 12 entrepreneurs suggest that the LSM can be validated upon practice. The practical implications of relate to the application of lean principles which enable entrepreneurs to validate their business idea on factual evidence from the market, thus increase the chances of success.

Keywords: New Venture Development, Lean Start-up Methodology, Customer Development, Evidence Based Entrepreneurship

Introduction

The topic of new venture creation has become a key consideration of both academic and practical interest in the field of business studies (Katz 1990; Bull and Willard 1993; Reynolds and White, 1997; Tkachev and Kolveried 1999) due to the increasing role and relevance of entrepreneurship and small businesses in the context of the modern, knowledge-based economy (Tan, 2003 and Campbell and Carayannis, 2016). The starting-up phase of creating and developing a new business venture is regarded as the most important area of the business life cycle, as this stage is critical as the new ventures must create viable and sustainable products/services and a business model to survive and prosper. (Bocken et al., 2014 and Salamzadeh and Kesim, 2015)

The traditional method of establishing new businesses is built upon the approach of business planning; the creation of a static plan by utilisation of strategic tools in order to describe the business, the products/services, it's market, the strategies for marketing and operations. (Michaluk, 2002).

High start-up failure rates are regarded as a major problem in developed economies, according to the most recent Global Start-up Ecosystem Report of the Start-up Genome Project (2017) 90% of the 3,200 assessed new ventures fail in the first five years of operation. The most likely causing factor of such phenomena is rooted in the traditional business planning approach, which focuses more on the execution of the plan, rather than the creation of products/service which satisfy a valid customer need (Lai and Lin, 2015). The traditional business planning model results in new businesses being less able to flexibly adapt. This rigidity is not reflecting to the new changes in the global economy particularly the increased uncertainty and international competition. In order to match new venture creation to such challenges, fundamentally different approaches have been developed for new venture start-ups highlighting the importance of the `searching for fit` process, especially in terms of product market fit, which has been identified as the main reason of new business failures. (Eisenmann, 2011)

The most comprehensive theoretical framework of business start-up up to date is the lean start-up methodology developed by Ries (2011), a successful Silicon Valley entrepreneur. This framework provides a revolutionary approach for creating a new business: instead of focusing on the creation and execution of a sound business plan, it advocates the creation of a new venture based on market demand and customer feedback. This aim has to be achieved through the adaptation of hypothesis- driven experimentation focusing on customer needs via the continuous cycle of releasing iterative products/services, and learning, thus eliminating the uncertainty surrounding the product development and business model creation process (Ries, 2011 and Eisenmann et al., 2012).

Critics of the lean start-up approach cite the lack of empirical evidence, the threats of releasing an inferior product to the market and the quality issues as primary disadvantages of the methodology. (Thiel, 2014; Burgstone, 2012; Heitmann, 2014 and Hussein, 2015). Additionally, funding issues associated with the implementation of the lean approach: as venture capitalists consider a detailed business plan with longterm financial projections in their investment decisions, businesses implementing the lean approach are viewed as unfundable. (Harrison, 2015; Pelling, 2015; Lewis, 2016 and Rowen, 2017). The lean start-up methodology has also been criticised for its lack of clarity and uncertainty in terms of boundaries of its implementation. (Blomberg, 2012; Kortman, 2013 and Ladd, 2016)

The question therefore emerges, that if traditional business planning is not suitable for the changing business environment is the new lean-start-up model more applicable for creating successful new ventures?

Ries (2011) argues that start-up success can be engineered according to the lean start-up principles. This statement suggests that the success of a new venture can be scientifically constructed, and can be learned. This statement projects far reaching implications in terms of both academic and applied business practice. Ries (2011) statement suggests that the lean start-up methodology provides solution for the problem of high failure rates of new ventures.

The academic relevance of this research is related to the argument of the academic literature; by providing empirical evidence to form empirical support scientific basis for the lean start-up methodology. This study aims to contribute to the theoretical debate between the advocates of the strategic business planning approach, (Greene and Hopp, 2017) and the new school of thought (Ries, 2011; Blank, 2012 and Maurya, 2015) in the academic field of new venture creation and development.

Practical importance of this study regards to the aim of confirming the lean start-up framework through the identification and evaluation of the critical success factors through the assessment and understanding of `real-life` experiences of entrepreneurs applying the lean start-up approach for their businesses. By providing empirical evidence, this study would contribute to the practical application of a viable business start-up framework which minimises the resources required and the risks related to new business creation, thus increasing the probability of success.

The primary aim of this study is to provide an empirical evidence on the practical ial implications of the lean start-up methodology (LSM) by analysing first-hand experiences of entrepreneurs who implemented this framework during their new venture creation. This research focuses on the critical success factors associated with the implementation of the LSM and seeks to evaluate the barriers to its implementation. Accordingly, the study aims to address the following research question: What are the critical success factors influencing the successful implementation of the LSM as validated through practical experience?

In order to answer the proposed research question, the following research objectives have been developed according to the review of the critics and key considerations linked to the application of the LSM; to identify the issues related to the minimum viable product element of the framework and the related quality considerations, to address the funding associated issues in the implementation process and to investigate the boundaries related to the LSM framework.

Literature Review

Economic Relevance of New Venture Development

The structural transformation trend of developed economies towards a knowledge based economy as opposed to the previous agricultural, labour and later service intensive systems has been acknowledged as a primary driver for change (Drucker, 1969). The knowledge-based economy is characterised by the increasing reliance on intellectual capabilities, knowledge intensive activities, the emphasis on information and innovation, and the utilisation of technological and scientific advancements to deliver products and services. (Meyer and Peng, 2016 and Caruso, 2016).

Entrepreneurial activity in relation to the formulation of new business ventures has high importance to a country's economic growth. The formulation of new companies is considered as an important indicator of a country's international competitiveness and economic development. (Lazear, 2004; Valliere and Peterson, 2009 and Kritikos, 2014).

A new venture is defined as a start-up business, by which an entrepreneur attempts to generate profits. Small ventures start up by identifying a business opportunity and allocating and organising the limited resources available to exploit it and generate financial gains (Gartner, 1985).

New venture creation in the context of this study refers to the economic activity by which an entrepreneur attempts to exploit a new business idea by utilising his limited resources. (Sobel, 2008). Entrepreneurs using capabilities and specific skills to turn a new idea into a business and make decisions in the process of new venture creation and development which leads to success (Kirkley, 2016). As per Shook, et al., (2003) venture creation central to entrepreneurial research and it considered as a key issue in entrepreneurship. Scholars in addressing new venture creation and development emphasised its processual nature, highlighting the relevance of the understanding of the pre-engagement and initial phases of entrepreneurial behaviour in relation to new ventures (Katz 1990; Bull and Willard 1993; and Reynolds and White, 1997). The academic research is focused on the identification of the various factors that influence

the early stage of the entrepreneurial process in relation to the individual's intention to create a business. (Krueger 1993 and Tkachev and Kolveried 1999).

Theoretical perspectives on the subject according to Hindle and Klyver (2011) attempt to conceptualise new venture creation in relation to the character traits of the individual entrepreneur. Gartner (1988) challenges the traditional view of new venture creation linked to individual characteristics and places the emphasis on the processual nature of the phenomena. Katz and Gartner (1988) and Vesper (1990) in attempting to conceptualise new venture creation propose that the process builds up by the intention, resource allocation, the establishment of boundaries and the exchange of resources across such boundaries within the newly established organisation.

Perspectives and Arguments on Business Start-up and Development

The traditional approach on business start-up proposes a linear and strategic framework focusing on creating a detailed business plan with formal sections based on various assumptions on the business environment, customer and market needs prior to starting up the new venture. (Van de Ven, et al., 1984; and George and Bock, 2011) As per Furr and Ahlstrom (2011) and Blank (2013), the traditional product development model of business start-ups funded on the primary activity of creating a business plan; following the static steps of describing the business opportunity in terms of problem and solution. This process involves the tasks of environmental analysis, the formulation of strategy implementation and control (Schendel and Hofer, 1979).

New approaches for business start-ups has been developed as a result of the challenges imposed by the extreme uncertainty of the dynamic business environment. Increasing competition, the need for continuous innovation and the volatile business environment encouraged the emergence of new theories of start-ups, focusing on the actual implementation and practical applicability in this new context. (Gustafsson and Qvillberg, 2012). Such frameworks aimed to provide practical considerations of the new venture creation focusing on the methods of turning an innovative idea into a viable business model. (Morris and Allen, 2005; McGrath, 2010; Zott, et al., 2011). Kraft (2016) summarises that these frameworks (as opposed to the traditional view on start-ups) characterised by an iterative approach and a focus on the `search for fit`.

The concept of `search for fit` is one of the core elements of the new theoretical frameworks. According to Osterwalder et al., (2010) searching for fit describes the process of value proposition development focusing on customer needs. This process involves the stages of starting up a new business: Problem-Solution Fit, Product-Market Fit and Business Model Fit.

Figure 1: Stages of a Start-up- Source: business2community.com (2016)

Problem-Solution Fit refers to the stage of identifying a problem and developing a value proposition to solve it (Amarsi, 2014). Product-Market Fit relates to the activities of raising interest and gathering feedback from early adopters/customers. The core tenant of the concept is to provide feedback from customers, thus evidence that the created value proposition is viable (Andreessen, 2007 and Ellis, 2011). Business Model Fit describes the creation of a viable business model around the developed value proposition (Morris et al., 2005).

Blank (2013) argues that the key difference between an operating company and a start-up linked to the business model: while existing business executing a strategic business plan, new start-ups are seeking for a viable one. The traditional method for starting up a business is concerned the implementation of a previously formulated plan, which is based on assumptions on the market and customers, following a similar process as the traditional product development (Furr and Ahlstrom, 2011; Netessine, 2015). As per Alvarez and Barney (2007) rigorous business planning and execution especially in the start-up phase may result in rigidities as entrepreneurs are not able to change direction according to the external environment, and to a certain extent following a business plan prevents learning which leads to failure. Blank (2013) refers to it as the successful execution of a wrong plan. Flexibility of a start-up has high importance: while existing companies have the knowledge on their product and market which results certainty about the environment, new start-ups due to their lack of knowledge navigate under high levels of uncertainty (McGrath and MacMillan, 1995).

A formal business plan may be applicable for an existing company, with significant knowledge, resources, capabilities and experience in the industry on which such strategic plan can be based. On the contrary, for a new venture, the uncertainty of the environment, the lack of knowledge on the market and the lack of resources impose significant challenges and limitations (Brinckmann, 2012 and Blank, 2012).

Advocates of the new theories argue that the increased uncertainty and volatility of the external business environment makes the traditional strategy planning method obsolete. In order to respond to the challenges, the changing environment imposes, entrepreneurs ought to adopt a more market oriented approach to start-up a successful business. New business ventures characterised by high uncertainty, which differs from the context of established companies (McGrath and MacMillan, 1995). Furthermore, the limited resources small businesses can obtain similarly result in the need for a fundamentally different framework (Blank, 2014). By a continuous cycle of hypothesis based experimentations through iterative product releases and customer feedback new start-ups are able to facilitate flexibility, control of resources and learning about their market. (Ashkenas and Finn, 2016) On the other hand Lange et al., (2007) and Gruber (2007) assert that an extensive formal business plan is a vital requirement for entrepreneurs seeking to attract venture capital, which is an important consideration in relation to the argument between the traditional and new approaches of new venture creation.

High start-up failure rates are widely considered as a major issue in advanced economies, the implemented formal business planning approach is most likely to be the causing factor of low start up survival rate. (Lai and Lin, 2015). According to Hack, et al., (2016) a high number of new ventures fail within a few years of their creation, this remarkably high rate of failure generated much attention.

Due to the volatility of the globalised marketplaces and the uncertainty of the business environment the traditional formal business planning method seems to be inadequate. According to the most recent Global Start-up Ecosystem Report of the Start-up Genome Project (2017), an estimated 90% start-ups fail within four years of their operation. In the United Kingdom despite the fact that the rate of starting up new businesses is steadily increasing- the 383,000 business births in 2015 were the highest recorded since 2000- more than 50% of new ventures are not able to last beyond five years. (Burn-Callander 2015). The statistical data on small business survival rates (Office for National Statistics, 2016) supports the argument proposed by the proponents of new start up theories; the high numbers of new business failures indicate certain problems. Most of the start-ups fail, most of the new ventures do not achieve their potential. (Qvillberg and Gustafsson, 2012)

Figure 2: The Reasons of Start-up Failure- Source: Cbsinsights.com (2016)

The most common cause of new venture failure is related to inadequate product market fit and the exhaustion of financial resources. Failed start-up refers to new businesses which ceased to exist within the first 4 years of their operations. (Johnson, 2012)

As per Eisenmann (2011), the frequent situation which certainly leads to the failure of a new business is that `they create the wrong products while wasting money on marketing and sales trying to sell such products`. Product market fit and the business failure due to the lack of understanding of the market and demands seems to be the number one reason failure- according to a recent study of C.B Insights (2014- Figure 2) analysing 156 failed start-ups- 42% of the cases.

The lean start-up methodology proposes a solution for high start-up failure, by offering a fundamentally different concept from the traditional business planning approach, and projecting that start-up success can be scientifically engineered, taught and learned (Ries, 2011)

The Lean Approach for New Venture Development

Ries (2011) a successful entrepreneur proposed a fundamentally different approach for new venture creation: the lean start-up approach. His comprehensive framework builds up on Blank`s (2011) customer development model incorporating a customer and market centric approach based on the continuous cycle of testing and redefining both the product and the business model, combining iterative and agile development techniques (Blank and Dorf, 2012). This framework offers a practical and evidence based solution for the problem of seeking a viable product and business model by providing a flexible approach for a new business start-up. (Gorash, 2015). According to Brinckmann et al (2010) and Patz (2013) the lean start-up methodology is centred on the process of trial-error learning, and thus constantly involves adjusting the product and the business model.

The theoretical foundation of the lean start-up methodology is rooted in the combination of lean manufacturing, customer development and agile software development (Balsler, 2015) The lean approach to manufacturing has been introduced by Ohno (1988); by the Toyota Production System- (TPS) is focused on the termination and minimisation of waste- activities which absorbs resources while not creating any value. The lean start-up methodology applies the same core principle of eliminate the wastage of primarily financial resources, thus optimising the need for initial funding. The concept also builds up on the concept of customer development model of Blank (2012). Based on the identification of market customer needs through iterative product release and validated learning. This process eliminates the uncertainty in the product development and ensures that the customer needs are met by the new product. Building on the feedback gathered throughout the hypothesis driven experimentations entrepreneurs are able to decide whether to persevere or pivot from the feature of the product or the business model tested. This cycle is repeated until the point that the hypothesis which refers to the viability of the new business venture is fully validated. (Nobel, 2011; Ries, 2011 and Blank, 2013).

Figure 3: The Lean Start-up Process-Developed by the Author

The LSM process (Figure 3) starts with the first phase: the formulation of a hypothesis or problem statement which is validated by customer conversations. In order to ensure success of a business, the entrepreneur ought to identify a specific problem of specific target market, on which the initial hypothesis to be generated. This first hypothesis ought to take the company's values, mission and vision into account (Blank, 2011 and Ries, 2011) key `leap of faith assumptions` are incorporated the initial hypothesis: the growth- how to achieve sustainable growth and the value hypothesis- how to create long-term value to the customers. In order to validate the hypothesis, the firm ought to find early adopters: customers who are actively seeking for solution to the problem identified by the firm. (Qvillberg and Gustafsson, 2012). The attractiveness of the market also needs to be explored and

measured according to competition, market size and market growth to determine the industry situation and evaluate the firm’s capabilities according to the industry.

The second phase of the process focusing on the development of the solution for the identified problem that this iterative process aims to create, is a product satisfying customer needs with the minimal resources needed for such a development. This is achieved by developing a Minimum Feature Set Hypothesis and a Minimum Viable Product. A Minimum Viable Product serves for testing the proposed solution (the product or any aspect of it) on the customers and collect feedback. This facilitates a development of knowledge by learning from the market throughout the repetitious cycles of build-measure- learn process. (Furr and Ahlstrom, 2011). The `get out of the building` strategy plays an important role in the second phase; the data gathered on customers is important in order to achieve growth and success.

Figure 4: LSM Method and the Search for Fit- Source: leanstartup.com (2016)

The first two phases primarily relate to the product development the third phase is focused on the validation of the business model, and scale of the new venture (which after the establishment of a product market fit), concentrates on the growth of the business. The lean start-up methodology successfully incorporates the concept of `search for fit` by developing the value proposition throughout the process. (Figure 4).

Table 1: Key Terms of the Lean Start-up Methodology

Key Terms of the Lean Start-up Methodology	
Validated Learning	A new approach for management by which the application of experimentation the entrepreneur became able to understand the customer needs, which is to sustainable business (Blank, 2012).
Build-Measure-Learn Feedback Loop	Refers to the iterative experimentation process of creating products, measuring customer's responses and learn from their feedback. This method enables accelerating, while minimising the resources used, thus facilitating a 'lean' approach (De Vet, 2013).
The Minimum Viable Product	In the element of build in the BLM process, refers to a minimum feature set product which suitable for testing on early adopters (Ries, 2011).
Innovation Accounting	The different approach for measuring productivity, the leap of faith assumptions and their learning translated measurable items and by the use of financial ratios enables to measure performance (Ries, 2011).
Steering Practices: Persevere or Pivot	Pivot refers to a major change, a structured course correction to test a fundamentally new hypothesis, whereas preserve your refers to the continuation of the course of action without change (Ries, 2011).
Engines of Growth	In order to accelerate the start-up through the BLM process entrepreneurs ought to focus the engines of growth: sticky growth engine- which aims to improve customer retention, viral growth engine- which linked to marketing and the paid engine of growth- which refers to advertising methods. These factors contribute to sustainable growth (Ries, 2011).

The benefits of Lean Start-up are linked that the framework enables entrepreneurs to minimise wastage while managing the risks of starting up a new business under extreme uncertainty. The approach is also suitable for limited budgets: by focusing on validated learning facilitates capital efficiency in the development of products/services suitable for market needs and in the search of a scalable business model. As customer feedback is integrated the model, the lean start-up methodology assures the success of the product development

Empirical Studies on Lean Start-ups

The approach of the lean start-up methodology is relatively new, there are only a few empirical researchers to be found discussing the topic. Table 2 outlines a summative overview on the academic researchers used for this study.

Table 2: Review of Empirical Studies on the Lean Start-up Method

Empirical Studies on the Lean Start-up Method		
Author (Year)	Implemented Method	Key Findings
Blomberg (2012)	Mixed- method- field Study and observations	Key issues with the traditional entrepreneurship theory Lack of clarity in the BML process
Gustafsson and Quillberg (2012)	Action Research	Identified barriers of LSM implementation: minimum viable product issues Scalability of the business model
De Wet (2013)	Qualitative- Multiple Case Study	E retailers successfully applied various elements of the LSM framework
Townend (2014)	Action Research	Clear vision to guide LSM implementation Importance of testing and customer feedback
Nirwan and Dhewanto (2014)	Qualitative- Case Study	Barriers of LSM implementation: MVP concept confusion quality issues of MVP results little interest of the customers
Ghorashi (2015)	Qualitative- interview method	BML challenges in relation to external knowledge sources in designing the tests Experiment evaluation is BML problematic.
Balser (2015)	Secondary research- statistical analysis	Elements of the LSM, links to the Business Model Canvas, Customer Development and Agile Development concepts
Salas Mart'inez (2016)	Qualitative- Multiple Case Study	Insufficient knowledge and understanding of the LSM hinders the application of the concept

Blomberg (2012) implemented a mixed method in assessing the lean start-up methodology; by combining a field study and observations identified the main issues with the traditional entrepreneurship theory. Important implication of this study relates to the finding that the lack of clarity in the iterative BML process imposes challenges to the practical application of the LSM concept. Gustafsson and Quillberg (2012) and Townend (2014) similarly applied in action research approach to investigate the practical application of the LSM, important findings related to the challenges of applying the MVP concept and the scalability of the business model. De Wet (2013) in facilitating a multiple case study concluded that online retailers successfully applied the various elements of the LSM framework. Nirwan and Dhewanto (2014) by conducting a qualitative Case study similarly highlighted the challenges of the MVP concept. Ghorashi (2015) based on a qualitative design identified the barriers of BML implementation and evaluation. Balser (2015) by implementing a secondary research links the principles of the LSM to the concept of Customer Development and Agile Development. Salas Martinez (2016) by investigating the approach revealed further considerations related to the LSM; by

facilitating a multiple case study approach determined the problematic area of is sufficient knowledge and understanding of the concept which limits the practical application of the lean approach for start-up development.

These studies pointed out considerable critical areas for further investigating to the critics and key considerations related to the lean start-up approach.

Criticism and Key Areas of Considerations

As this study focuses on the critical success factors of the lean start-up methodology, therefore the assessment of criticism linked to the approach is essential. Based on a further review on the available literature on criticising the practical applicability and viability of the lean concept on creating a new venture is inconsistent, subjective and opinionated, assuming that the methodology has several flaws linked to the core concept, consequently it cannot be applied outside the domain of digital new ventures. Table 3 presents the relevant critics and the areas of considerations of the LSM framework identified from the secondary data analysis.

Table 3: Critics and Areas of Considerations of the Lean Start-up Methodology

Critics and Areas of Considerations of the Lean Start-up Methodology		
Author (Year)	Findings	Questions
Thiel (2014)	BML is the replacement of the decision making based on a strong vision and determination	How the vision of the founder is represented in the LSM?
Burgstone (2012)	Examples of disruptive innovations based on innovative ideas and products with full features.	What are the requirements of features translates to viability?
Hussein (2015)	Dangers of quality issues in relation to MVP	Is MVP applicable for businesses other than digital? Sacrifice of quality?
Heitmann (2014)	MVP may result bad initial impressions in customers The role of marketing and R&D is not considered in the LSM approach	MVP and quality considerations Are marketing and R&D considerations worth to incorporate in the process?
Nirwan and Dhewanto (2014)	Barriers of the LSM in practice: MVP concept causes confusion, poor quality product results little interest from customers, thus result [sic] feedback in the BLM process.	When to release MVP? What are the requirements of minimum viability?
IMPLICATIONS: MVP- inferior product to the market and quality issues, lack of strong vision, Build-Measure-Learn process, , testing and refining the business model, lack of marketing and R&D		
Pelling (2015)	Lean start-ups are un-fundable Business angels requirements are fundamentally missing form a lean start-up	How the investors' requirements can be matched in applying the LSM?
Rowen (2017)	Initial funding issues due to the extending trend of seed funding phase.	Is the LSM approach provides solution to the seed funding phase?
Walton (2015)	Industries of high barriers of entry require large initial investment, thus the lean approach is useless in such sectors.	How to acquire funding in high entry barrier industries as per the LSM?
Maurya (2015)	LSM is cheap myth Need for resources Possible solution: bootstrapping	Is the LSM necessarily cheap? What are the solutions for early stage resource needs?
IMPLICATIONS Funding issues associated with implementing the lean approach, seed funding phase, business angels' requirements, the lack of long term plans and financial projections, risks related to dynamically changing business model.		
Blomberg (2012)	Low tech manufacturing may implement the lean approach Lack of clarity in relation to the BML process	Can the BML process clearly defined?
Kortman (2013)	LSM results internal uncertainty	When to finish the BML process? When to scale? When the business starts generating profits?
Ladd (2016)	LSM is applicable in practice, however relevant considerations linked to false negatives in BML (the rejection of good ideas based on early feedback) No clear links between the continuous BLM and success	How to eliminate false negatives? How to facilitate an effective BML Cycle?
IMPLICATIONS Unclear boundaries in relation to the BLM process, business model and the lack of empirical evidence		

The first identified area of criticism is related to the LSM approach's core concept of Minimum Viable Product and the quality issues linked to it. The most acknowledged critic of the LSM; Thiel (2014) argues that the fundamental concept of the framework is the replacement of the decision-making process: the emphasis on quick qualification and pivot in the process of Build- Measure and Learn, he claims, is contrary to a strong vision and concentrated effort to bring a new and innovative idea into existence. Burgstone (2012) supports Thiel's argument by highlighting that disruptive innovations; products and services were the first competitors in the

marketplace, bringing a new and innovative full product to the market instead of a minimum viable one for testing.

Hussein (2015) emphasises scepticism in the practical implementation of the build measure and learn process, although utilising a minimum viable product is sensible and practical in the world of digital businesses, the drive to be lean and minimal in product development results in the sacrificing of quality, hence the MVP concept is not applicable for more complex or high quality products. Hussein (2015) argues that these drives can paralyse creativity which may lead to inferior product development and ultimately the failure of a new business venture.

Heitmann (2014) similarly concludes that although the approach is making sense, the minimum viable product concept must be applied with caution due to quality considerations. He concludes that the key related issues that the MVP might not deliver satisfactory quality and the lean concept may lead to release inferior products which results in bad impressions amongst customers. Furthermore, he highlights that the approach does not take the role of marketing and research and development into consideration. Nirwan and Dhewanto (2014) in discussing the barriers of the lean start-up methodology state that the MVP is likely to create confusion, and that an early release of a poor-quality product as MVP for testing may not capture the customers' interest, and thus may produce false results in the process of BML.

This highlights an implication for this study in terms of the lack of clarity in requirements of minimum viability, the role of the entrepreneur's vision in the process and the quality issues linked to the practical application of the MVP concept. Additional areas; the lack of emphasis in marketing and R&D also identified.

The next field of argument is linked to the funding issues associated with implementing the lean approach. Lean Start-up companies facing this problem in the early stages of the financing cycle. After an initial, own investment is acquired for starting up the business, the attraction of seed capital is vital for further development. Seed capital is generally acquired from business angels, who provide backing in exchange for a stake from the business. Investors in making investment decisions evaluate the business founder, his/her understanding of the market, the product and the financial opportunity to invest in the start-up. (Harrison, 2015) The problem of lean start-up funding arose from the differences between the LSM and the traditional business planning approach: prototype businesses - which is the core concept of the lean start-up method - are rarely suitable for seed funding, and the lack of long-term financial plans it makes impossible to acquire backing from sources other than bootstrapping or crowdfunding (Lewis, 2016).

Pelling (2015) claims that lean start-ups are un-fundable. Early stage start-ups are predominantly backed by business angels. The utilisation of LSM due to the lack of long-range planning and future financial projections is intrinsically un-fundable as investors will not back start-ups without a solid plan, a viable product and customer/

market knowledge from the start. The risks associated with a dynamically changing the business model also imposes barriers for financing a lean start-up. Rowen (2017) in assessing the current state of start-up funding also concludes according to his analysis of the overall start-up funding activity between 2010 and 2016 that seed funding period of start-ups have been increased to two years. This imposes significant challenges for start-ups as there are limited types of funding available in seed funding period.

In addition, Maurya (2015) states that there is a fundamental misconception about the LSM approach and lean does not means cheap and low quality products, rather it refers to the elimination of resources wastage, and thus increase in efficiency. To develop products, the acquisition of external resources, especially backing is essential, however funding of lean start-ups is a critical area. Maurya (2015) offers a possible solution to the issue: bootstrapping, which refers to the method of self-funding, however this proves rarely enough for establishing a business. Walton (2015) highlights that industries of high entry barriers impose significant investment need for start-ups, due to the size of the minimum viable product required make the lean startup methodology pointless. Relevant outtake from this argument for this study is the identification of the funding issues as a critical area for further investigation

The third established area of issues related to the LSM framework is linked to the unclear boundaries in the practical implementation of the methodology especially in the areas of testing and refining the business model. Blomberg (2012) in addressing the LSM applicability outside digital new ventures concludes that low tech manufacturing may also successfully implement the lean start-up approach, however there is a lack of clarity linked to the tests and feedbacks of physical products, which results uncertainty in the Build Measure and Learn- BLM process. This issue is also confirmed by the empirical study of Ghorashi (2015)

Kortman (2013) argues that the core problem with the framework is internal uncertainty. As the lean concept aims to eliminate external uncertainty it creates internal uncertainty. Entrepreneurs are unclear as to at what point the product developed may become viable, when to finish the BML process, and begin to scale. Furthermore, there is a high level of uncertainty linked to the time when the venture will actually generate profit and ready to scale.

Ladd (2016) in summarising the research of the Cleantech Accelerator Program- a study of ten years - states that in general the lean start-up method is a workable concept. In particular, the study suggests that there is no relationship between the numbers of validated tests within the continuous build measure and learn process, and the success of the teams assessed, which means more qualification is not necessarily yields better results. He also highlights that there is a strong possibility that the implemented lean approach produces false negatives- wrong test results due to the MVP concept. This is linked to the possible error of the LSM approach which does not give a clear rule of finishing tests and begin the scaling process of a new

venture. Implementations to this study relate to the investigative areas of unclear boundaries in relation to the BLM process, the scalability of business model and the lack of empirical evidence.

Synthesis

The literature review places the concept of lean approach methodology in the context of the knowledge-based economy and the entrepreneurship domain of academic interest. By highlighting the current problem of high start-up failure explains the paradigm shift from a traditional business plan and execution based thinking to a fundamentally new theoretical foundation: evidence-based entrepreneurship. The customer development model of Blank (2012) and the `search for fit` efforts of start-ups explained as it forms the basis of understanding the lean start-up methodology. The principles of the lean approach for new venture development has been detailed, the key terminology defined as well as the core tenant of the concept: the focus on resource efficiency. The empirical studies on the lean start-up has been reviewed in order to inform the further secondary research on the key success factors of the lean start-up approach. The literature review identified 3 distinct areas which considered as critical in the practical implementation of the concept: the confusion of the Minimum Viable Product concept, the funding -related challenges and the issues related to the clarity of the practical implementation of the methodology.

Method

Approach to Theory Development, Strategy and Design

The adopted interpretivist philosophical stance of this study leads to the methodological choice of a qualitative method of inquiry. A qualitative research approach, according to Hogan et al., (2009) is a suitable choice for investigating a specific phenomenon through the analysis of human experiences. The qualitative method as opposed to the quantitative research method is an interpretive, pragmatic approach focusing on a small sample through which a specific subject of interest is examined. A qualitative method of inquiry is more sufficient in attempting to develop a pragmatic and deeper understanding of a particular phenomenon, taking complexity and subjectivity into consideration, unlike reducing the observations into single variables as in quantitative approaches. (Flick, 1998 and Marshall and Rossman, 2006). In addition, an implemented qualitative approach is more appropriate with regards to the research aim of understanding the lean start-up methodology through personal experiences of entrepreneurs.

Data Collection

With regards to research design, a mono method of data collection has been utilised: the primary data has been collected by semi-structured interviews, involving practitioners of the lean start-up methodology. The interview method for collecting primary data defined by Boyce and Neale (2006) as a qualitative technique which involves a small sample of respondents and focuses on the exploration of their perspective and experience on a particular phenomenon. The interview method has been selected in alignment of the purpose of this study: attempting to develop a deeper understanding on the critical factors of the lean startup framework for new venture development. The interview method provides the advantage of enabling the researcher to obtain detailed information on the subject through which the framework of the lean start-up methodology can be further assessed.

Semi structured interviews, as a mean of collecting qualitative data has been conducted with practitioners of the lean start-up methodology.

The reasons for using semi structured interviews over structured or unstructured interviews relates to the combination of the benefits this technique provides; the combination of a pre-determined open ended set of questions which enables to engage in formal interview process according to the interview guide containing a list of topics to be covered, and in the meantime allows trajectories from the discussion if necessary. This qualitative method of inquiry, preceded by the development of relevant and meaningful questions with regards to the research area, permits the identification of new themes emerging from the discussion.

In order to conduct the interview process Internet mediated- email interviews has been utilised. This advanced type of interview refers to an asynchronous setting in which the communication between the interviewer and the respondent taking place independently from place and time. The main reason behind the implementation of email interviews in comparison with a face-to-face type interview is that it grants extended access to participants by avoiding the setting of a mutually convenient time to conduct the interview, thus increase response rates thus effectiveness. (Coomber, 1997 and Meho 2006) As per Bampton and Cowton (2002) by permitting the delay between the communication email interviews also provides sufficient time for the respondent to develop his/her responses.

Secondary data has been gathered with the aim of informing the research objectives, to develop the critical aspects of the lean start-up methodology application for new venture creation and to support the findings of this study. Secondary data collection employed keyword and phrase searches in online academic databases such as ProQuest, EbscoHost and Jstor.

In selecting an appropriate sample nonprobability sampling techniques have been implemented: a combination of purposive and snowball sampling. Purposive/selective sampling refers to the technic in which the researcher based on

the sample selection on the criteria of who can provide valuable information with regards to this subject area. The nature of the topic researched justifies the implementation of a selective sampling, furthermore the type of expert sampling is the most suitable as a specific expertise on the lean start-up methodology is required from the respondents to gain a detailed understanding of the areas of considerations.

To identify experts, an Internet search has been conducted on various online platforms engaging in discussions on the lean start-up methodology such as the Lean Start-up Circle London, the Leanstart-upyorkshire.org the leanstartupmachine.com and the Start-ups.co.uk.

Snowball/ chain referral sampling defined as a respondent driven sampling technique, which takes advantage of the professional or social networks of identified respondents, thus providing the researcher and expanding set of potential respondents. (Atkinson and Flint, 2001) Following Noy (2008) snowball sampling is identified as the easiest method to assess experts and adopters of the lean start-up methodology.

By combining the two sampling techniques the purposive sampling enabled to identify potential respondents with relevant expertise, and snowballing provided an appropriate number of respondents from the professional networks of the initial respondents. The inclusion criteria for reaching a specific population is aligned with the purpose of the study; including participants who were involved in the practical application of the lean start-up methodology, thus able to provide valuable information with regards to the practical implementation of the theory.

The decision on a suitable sample size considered both practical and theoretical reasons. Practical reasons considered the qualitative research design and strategy while practical reasons included convenience, time and cost constraints of this study. As according to Saunders et al. (2014) qualitative studies do not require a determined sample population as the focus of the research is on a theoretical concept rather than on a population; consequently, the sample size depends on the research objectives and on the considerations of credibility and validity. A sample frame of 12 respondents establishes the validity and credibility of this qualitative research. Internet access has been chosen to establish contact with the respondents and process the interviews.

Analysis Procedure

This exploratory study employing a grounded theory strategy, utilising the lean startup methodology guiding the theoretical concept to determine the areas of investigation then subsequently attempting to generate a theory with regards to such areas by the discovery of conceptual categories and explanations, hence meeting the research objectives and answering the research question.

Grounded theory as per Bryant and Charmaz (2007) enables to conceptualise a phenomenon through the systematic process of discovering, developing and verifying a theory by systematic data collection and analysis. The research principle behind grounded theory is neither inductive nor deductive, but combines both in a way of abductive reasoning, combining the research borrowed again with a pragmatic course of action. Following Reichertz (2010), abductive reasoning is the most appropriate logic to be applied in grounded theory. The interpretivist philosophical foundation and the extant of existing knowledge on the lean start-up methodology also justifies the strategy selection.

This research with regards to time horizon is a cross-sectional study, the assessment of the critical success factors of the lean start-up methodology taking place in a particle time, due to time constraints

In order to explain and make sense of the data collected by the interviews thematic content analysis has been applied. Content analysis according to Cassell and Symon (2004) and Saunders et al. (2014) involves the process of systematic classification and description of the data, and sufficient for gaining an in-depth understanding on the subject area by enabling to identify recurring themes, hence providing a meaningful interpretation of the data. Content analysis, an observational research method utilised in order to systematically assess and evaluate of communication content, is associated with qualitative studies, allowing to analyse human experiences through analysing communication. (Kolbe and Burnett, 1991)

This research applies thematic analysis technique which commonly associated with qualitative research emphasising the identification of themes/patterns emerging from the data collected. Such themes are relevant in relation to the developed research questions. The process of thematic analysis follows the phases of transcription, generation of codes, searching, defining and labelling themes emerged from the data and producing a discussion of qualitative reasoning. (Saunders et al. 2014)

In justifying the implementation of thematic content analysis it can be stated that this technique allows the researcher to interpret the themes identified and by providing flexibility it permits to interlink the findings of the analysis with the literature review in answering the research question. This flexibility also allows the implementation of data source triangulation with the aim of validating and increasing the credibility by cross verifying the secondary data sources with the findings derived from the analysis of the primary data. (Olsen, 2004)

In summary, his study adopts the philosophical framework of interpretivism to guide its development, to achieve the research objectives and facilitate a deep level of understanding is based on the subjective experiences of the experts. According to the interpretivist philosophical stance this study facilitates a qualitative method of enquiry which implies an abductive approach for theory development. For collecting primary data, a mono-method of data collection proposed: semi-structured

interviews. In order to facilitate a convenient interview process Internet mediated-email interviews has been utilised. A sample size of 12 experts on the lean start-up methodology is proposed, achieved by the combination of purposive and snowball sampling techniques. This cross-sectional, exploratory study employs a grounded theory strategy. The data analysis process utilises the technique of thematic content analysis. The ethical considerations are ensured by acquiring and informed consent from the interviews, by assuring confidentiality and anonymity.

Findings and Discussion

Preliminary Questions

The preliminary section of the interviews was focused on establishing rapport with the interviewees and on the introduction of the topic as well as the main areas for discussion in general. Opening questions posed to the interviews involved for general ossification according to business types, thus establishing credibility and validity of the collected data. (Table 4).

Table 4: Classification of Interviewees by Business Type and Years of Experience

Initial Classification of the Interviewees			
Interviewee Code No.	Business Type	Years of Experience	No. of Interviewees
<i>Respondents 1; 2;3</i>	<i>Business Consultancy</i>	10+	3
<i>Respondents 4; 5;6</i>	<i>Start-up Consultancy</i>	7+	3
<i>Respondents 7;8;9</i>	<i>Software Development</i>	1+	3
<i>Respondent 10</i>	<i>Dietary Supplements/Health Foods</i>	2	1
<i>Respondent 11</i>	<i>Hospitality/ Catering</i>	5	1
<i>Respondent 12</i>	<i>Publishing House</i>	5	1
Total Number of Respondents- Target Sample			12

The initial classification of interviews highlights the variety in which to lean start-up methodology has been adopted in practice, which indicates that the concept is applicable outside software development and online business settings. This suggests the flexibility afforded by the LSM approach in being applied to multiple business settings.

Issues Related to the Minimum Viable Product Element of the LSM

The first discussion area is focused on achieving the first research objective with regards to assessing the issues of the LSM framework linked to the minimum viable product element, its implications and related criticism in terms of product/service quality. Key issue emergent from a review of the relevant literature is that an early introduction of an MVP to the market may negatively impact on the customers' perception of the product/service. In such instances, the concern relates to the failure in the delivery of satisfactory quality (Heitmann, 2014 and Hussein, 2015).

Additional issues identified related to the requirements of minimum viability, to the confusion around the MVP concept and to the sacrifice of product/service quality in order to facilitate a quicker build- measure- learn cycle process (Nirwan and Dhewanto, 2014) which forms the basis of the LSM concept. (See:2.3.1) the guiding interview questions (Appendix 1) were focused on exploring interviews the use and practical experiences concerning the concept of MVP.

Table 5:1: Minimum Viable Product Considerations

Themes related to the Minimum Viable Product Considerations			
Themes/ Main Categories	Sub Categories	No. of Responses	Frequency
MVP as a strategic process	<i>MVP confusion</i>	11	91.6%
	<i>No rule</i>	10	83.3%
	<i>MVP for learning about product/ market</i>	8	66%
	<i>MVP for viability testing</i>	2	16.6%
	<i>Experiment to test assumptions</i>	6	50%
Determinants of viability: product and market	<i>Viable if the product provides value to customers</i>	5	41.6%
	<i>Viability determined by the market</i>	8	66%
	<i>Balance between minimum and viability</i>	7	58.3%
	<i>Minimum prototype vs MVP</i>	3	25%
Importance of early adopters	<i>Attraction of potential buyers</i>	6	50%
	<i>Building an audience</i>	8	66%
	<i>Test on first prospects</i>	10	83.3%

Table 5:2: Minimum Viable Product Considerations- Frequency of Key Themes

Table 5 presents the themes identified from the analysis of the interview transcripts. The most important theme which emerged from the discussion related to the process implementing the minimum viable product element of the LSM framework. In considering this element, the most frequent opinion of the interviewees related to the confusion surrounding the MVP concept.

“MVP as a term might be misleading and vague. Often it derails the people from the core concept of the lean approach: the minimisation of investment for the maximisation of learning. In fact, the minimum viable product doesn’t have to be a product at all.” (Respondent 5- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

“MVP is more of a strategy, not a single one-time thing. The term ‘product’ in it is actually a misnomer.” (Respondent 8- Software Development, 1+ years of experience)

“MVP can be an actual prototype your product with the least amount of features which make it viable to the market, but your MVP does not have to be a product at all. Viable if it delivers value to your customers. “(Respondent 11-Catering Industry, 5 years of experience)

“The minimum viable concept is rather a confusing it is not refers actually to a physical product but the minimum thing, even a small feature of the product which lets you learn about your market and customers on the resource efficient way.” (Respondent 4- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

All of the respondents agreed on the statement that the minimum viable product element is less a rule for application and more a strategic perspective towards the learning process of the market. The MVP is a technique to facilitate the build - measure - learn cycle, used to test any assumptions of the product or market. By determining the assumption, the idea is to find out the smallest possible experiment to test the assumption and input the results to correct the current course. Significant

number of interviewees-10 also clarified that there are no set rules in applying the minimum viable product approach but rather there are broader principles which guide the process.

“There are no rules, only best practices, however there are shortcuts or simpler ways to do these things right. There is no rule that you have to validate all of your assumptions, nor that you must introduce a cheap version of your product to the market. In fact, there are no rules of the lean start-up methodology, only guidelines and principles which you must evaluate if applicable to your product or business model. (Respondent 2- Business Consultancy, 10+ years of experience)

“The MVP concept is all about facilitating an experiment in the actual market, which allows you to learn from your customers about your product or and the feature of it and validate your assumption based on the feedback of the market. According to the results you can either modify your product or crack on with the development. What is minimum depends on your product and what is viable depends on your market, there are no set rules.” (Respondent 8- Software Development, 1+ years of experience)

According to the discussions with the respondents, the term minimum viable product does not necessarily refer to an actual, physical product but rather an approach to achieve validated learning, where the term is best described as a strategic approach for learning from the market, an experimental way to test assumptions about the product or the business model on customers.

The second most frequent theme identified concerns the determinants of viability in the minimum viable product quality and the concerns linked to the introduction of an `inferior` product to the market. A relevant opinion, that viability is determined by the product and the market has been emphasised by most of the respondents. The importance of finding the right balance between the minimum features and the viability were also found to be an important category.

“There is no rule that your MVP has to be cheap. The minimum feature set in your MVP required to test your initial hypothesis, this can be determined according to your target market” (Respondent 12- Publishing House, 5 years of experience)

“Lean start-up sometimes gets criticised for the wrong reasons, i.e. people who have misunderstood what it’s all about and don’t get the outcome they expect as a result of misapplying or ignoring basic principles.” (Respondent 4- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

“Most importantly you have to find the right balance between minimum and viable, which factors are highly dependent on your product and customers.” (Respondent 1- Business Consultancy, 10+ years of experience)

It seems to be evident that viability is achieved if the product provides value to the intended customers, which value depends on the determination of a minimum feature

set of a product/service which solve the identified and validated problem of the intended customers. It is important to note that the interviewees clarified the idea that the MVP approach in case if it's applied for product development, a minimum prototype is not equivalent to a minimum viable product.

“While the minimum prototype products can be seen as a beta version of the actual product, the minimum viable product concept enables to test your core business hypothesis, any feature of the product idea in a way that saves a lot of time and efforts.” (Respondent 1- Business Consultancy, 10+ years of experience)

The last relevant theme identified from the interviews is related to the importance of early adopters. In applying the MVP strategy criticism is often linked to quality considerations Heitmann (2014) and Nirwan and Dhewanto (2014).

The most frequent sub-category identified was the requirement of building and engaging with an audience before introducing an actual product to the market.

“The first test is not the test of your product, it is the test of your offer. Customers have to want your product. If you don't have an MVP, you have a `friends and family release` to test your offer on them.” (Respondent 5- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

“It is best to start building an audience around the problem domain by getting active in social media, comment on blogs or even starting a blog. This will be useful later on to test your MVP.” (Respondent 8- Software Development, 1+ years of experience)

This idea seems to be eliminating the concerns of introducing an `inferior` product to the market which criticism has been proposed by Heitmann (2014). By engaging with early adopters start-ups are able to develop a suitable and somewhat separated field for facilitating hypothesis testing thus validate an idea by the feedback of customers.

The further literature searches and review of the aspects on the lean start-up methodology which emerged from the discussions with LSM experts aimed to ascertain the findings of the interview analysis.

Ries (2011) defines the minimum viable product as the *“version of a new product which allows a team to collect the maximum amount of validated learning about customers with the least effort.”* In case that the MVP is applied as a Minimum Prototype, the findings support these definition recognising the minimum viable product as a beta version with a minimum feature set. Kortman (2012) highlights the issue of identifying the point of viability. The interview analysis defined that the minimum feature set which determines viability is depending on the actual product and the market, there are no set of rules to be implemented. Maurya (2015) argues that lean start-ups are not necessarily cheap, being lean is about being efficient with the resources in delivering value to the market. Ramli (2014) much like the

interviews agrees on that the lean start-up methodology is a set of guidelines and emphasises the importance of critical thinking over of adhering to a rigid framework. The practical application of the LSM and the approach of MVP depends on the product and the market.

On the other hand, an important contradiction with the available literature relates to the finding that the minimum viable product is seen rather a strategy in the practical application of the concept. While Ries (2011) definition concerns the term minimum viable product literally, it seems that in practice it makes more sense to consider it as a strategy approach, rather than a fixed prescriptive application. Considering the MVP principles in a strategy sands seems to be similar to the customer development approach of Blank (2012) which emphasises the achievement of product/market fit through validating hypotheses by customer feedback.

A relevant finding is that engaging with early adopters start-ups are able to eliminate the concerns related to product quality. Tullman (2014) argues that the creation of a `minimum viable audience` is a vital requirement to succeed with the MVP concept. This opinion is supported by Pelling`s (2015) criticism arguing that making a bad first impression by releasing products with minimal features to the market is hard to rectify. Pelling (2015) suggests that by building a separate, initial audience and applying the MVP strategy or introducing a Minimum Prototype to such audience in order to gain feedback and facilitate validated learning could be a viable option.

Concluding the first area of discussion key finding is that the minimum viable product can be interpreted as an approach for customer driven experimentation, a way of thinking according to a set of guidelines and principles proposed by the lean start-up methodology building up on the customer development model. Further implication of the findings is that market and product specific aspects are forming the actual implementation of the concept, which suggests the flexibility of the lean start-up methodology.

Funding Issues in the Practical Implementation of the LSM Concept

The second area of discussions is linked to the second objective of this study to address the funding associated issues in the implementation process of the lean start-up.

Important considerations emerge from the literature review, according to Pelling (2015) the dynamically changing business model and the implemented strategic approach of lean start-ups makes them un-fundable by business angels. Lewis (2016) argues that a prototype business such as start-ups are rarely suitable for seed funding. This problem is particularly important for start-ups aiming to develop prototypes-MVPs which require a substantial amount of investment.

Table 6:1: Lean Start-up Funding Considerations

Themes related to Lean Start-up Funding Considerations			
Themes/ Main Categories	Sub categories	No. of Responses	Frequency
Initial funding options	<i>Bootstrapping</i>	9	75%
	<i>Own Money/Self-funding</i>	11	91.6%
	<i>Crowdfunding</i>	10	83.3%
	<i>Govt. Grants and Schemes</i>	8	66%
	<i>Lean= resource effectiveness</i>	10	83.3%
	<i>Capital efficiency in core of LSM</i>	9	75%
Funding depends on stages of start-up development	<i>Measuring progress- evidence</i>	6	50%
	<i>Understanding which type of funding available each stage</i>	9	75%
	<i>Stages of Development</i>	12	100%
	<i>Stage/risk ratio</i>	4	33.3%
	<i>investors</i>	3	25%
Considerable opportunities for funding in later stages	<i>understanding of LSM approach</i>	3	25%
	<i>Lean funding circles</i>	2	16.6%
	<i>Start-up accelerators, incubators</i>	8	66%
	<i>Seed and early stage investment funds</i>	7	58.3%
	<i>Country specific start-up funding landscape</i>	7	58.3%
Additional Themes of Funding Problems	<i>Business Angels and Venture Capitalist requirements</i>	10	83.3%
	<i>Valuation Issues</i>	3	25%
	<i>Contractual expectations</i>	1	8.3%

Table 6:2: Lean Start-up Funding Considerations- Frequency of Key Themes

Table 6 presents the main themes according to the categories identified from the data analysis in relation to the second research objectives related to the considerations of lean start-up funding.

The most important theme emerged from the interviews according to occurrences is the linkage between funding and the stage of development of a lean start-up. The connection between the funding cycle and the lean start-up methodology is emphasised by most of the respondents; stating that the recognition between the linkages of start-up milestones and the funding types available for them is vital in new venture creation and development.

For the pre-start-up phase, two initial funding options have been identified: self-funding/ bootstrapping and crowdfunding. Bootstrapping refers the utilisation of own financial resources, whereas crowdfunding is the practice of raising financial contributions from a large number of people (Howe, 2006 and Abney, 2012).

“Lean start-up methodology and bootstrapping are complementary, both realises that efficiency with the available resources by eliminating waste is important, most lean start-ups begin with self-funding initially and work their way up through a method customer acquired funding.” (Respondent 11- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

“Crowdfunding platforms give considerable opportunities for start-ups applying lean methods. Alternatively, in the UK the various government schemes and incentives are available for start-ups seeking for funding “Respondent 2- Business Consultancy, 10+ years of experience)

The data analysis revealed that the method of crowdfunding in the inception stage is considered as an alternative to self-funding/bootstrapping a start-up. Crowdfunding is an innovative way for entrepreneurs to raise investment from a large number of people by methods based on donations, rewards or equity/debt. (Herbert, 2014)

Crowdfunding platforms might be a suitable method to engage with early adopters as well. As the lean start-up methodology's core tenant is resource effectiveness, the concept enables entrepreneurs to apply a capital efficient approach for creating a new business venture.

The second identified theme of the interviews is the notion that the type of funding source depends on the stages of start-up development. According to the interviews this problem of start-up funding is not solely an issue of lean start-ups, but rather a general problem of new venture creation with regards to raising capital.

"The harsh reality is that these days you won't get external funding until you are already making money and you have some sort of proven track record." (Respondent 2- Business Consultancy, 10+ years of experience)

"Financial metrics are important; it doesn't matter how bright the future seems to be for your business you have to show results to the investors in order to get funding." (Respondent 12- Publishing House, 5 years of experience)

As in the early stages of new venture acquiring funding being problematic, investors require evidence of the viability and profitability of the business idea, therefore entrepreneurs must rely on their own resources in the first place. However, it seems that the lean approach might be effective in these early stages as the LSM highlights the importance of efficiency.

"Being lean means being efficient with the resources, this forms the core concept of the lean start-up methodology." (Respondent 6-Catering Industry, 5 years of experience)

"Lean refers to efficiency; efficiency with efforts and efficiency with resources. The lean approach focuses on the development of a so-called 'low burn' start-up development. (Respondent 5- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

The lean approach by quickly and effectively getting customer feedback on the minimum viable product optimises the utilisation of resources. According to a respondent, applying the lean principles in the early stages can be combined with the traditional business planning which is a requirement of early seed investors:

"Getting a prototype to quickly test on the market provides more information to build a clear business plan which would be helpful in acquiring investment from angels or VCs" (Respondent 2- Business Consultancy, 10+ years of experience)

From the interviews, considerable opportunities for funding have emerged in later stages of new venture development for example government backed start-up loans, grants and other incentives such as TSB schemes, innovation grants, R&D tax credits, or regional growth funds (Tenner, 2017) may be applicable for the business. The availability of these options are dependent on country specific factors and the investors understanding of the LSM approach.

“The stages of start-up according to the lean framework are linked to the problem/solution fit, where self-funding is applicable, product/market fit, which is the stage of Angel funding and the scaling point where VC funding can be sought.” (Respondent 5- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

“Entrepreneurs must explore the available opportunities in each stage and must consider the requirements for eligibility.” (Respondent 1- Business Consultancy, 10+ years of experience)

The respondents emphasised that the key aspect of start-up funding is timing, the reaching of certain lean start-up milestones is linked to a certain type of investment available. Key finding is that the investors ought to understand the lean approach which consequently impacts on the decision of funding start-ups implementing the lean approach. Start-up accelerators, incubators and other seed funding and early stage investment funds might be considered if the actual new venture requires more capital in the early development stages.

Additional themes of funding problems relate to the valuation issues of investors: because of the dynamically changing business model and the feature set of the product in lean start-ups, investors may find it difficult to evaluate the viability of a new venture, thus making investment decisions. The same reasons would make contractual expectations on equity needed and returns of an investment impossible.

Further literature searches and review of the aspects suggested by the interviewees' correlates with the specific areas pointed out by the interviews relating to the initial funding issues. Funding imposes a problem not just in relation to the lean start-ups but for start-ups in general. To find solutions for the problems of business access to early stage funding therefore has increased importance. Start-ups access to funding is constrained by demand and supply side weaknesses: while businesses are not investment ready and the owners do not know how to “sell” their business to investors, such weaknesses compromise the supply side interventions from the business Angels. (OECD, 2017) Furthermore the UK setting of start-up funding is very complex and potentially confusing. (Tenner, 2017) The various options for getting start-up funding are stretching from crowdfunding, debt funding, incubators, business angels and venture capitalists to various options of government grants and schemes. All these options can be linked to stages of a start-up (Figure 1) and the process of search for fit proposed in the LSM framework (Figure 5)

As per Maurya (2015) the lean approach focuses on the maximisation of resources before acquiring ones, and thus facilitates the elimination of waste. He also argues premature fundraising is considered wasteful in the LSM approach and that in the case a large initial investment is required by start-up, crowdfunding is an adequate technique for the lean start-up apart from self-funding. Worren (2014) and Briggman (2017) also considers crowdfunding as the most applicable technique for acquiring early stage funding for start-ups; as it is providing a way for validating the idea, the

product and the business model. These suggested opinions support the findings of the interview analysis.

Important contradiction of the findings with the available literature relates to capital efficiency. Walton (2015) argues that industries of high entry barriers impose significant funding need for start-ups, and due to the amount required to develop a minimum prototype makes the application of the LSM pointless.

The additional literature search also proposes a considerable solution with regards to the identified valuation problems investors may face in evaluating lean start-ups. Blank (2015) proposed an applicable solution for measuring progress of lean start-ups: the investment readiness levels. The idea applies the concept of technology readiness level metrics implemented in space engineering, which according to Mankins (1995) is a system for systematically measuring the maturity of a technology in a program. Investment readiness level achieves the same; by a software based application it enables the evaluation of a business model (Hudson, 2015).

In concluding the second area of discussion – the funding related issues of the lean start-up methodology: the findings support the existence of problems and the assessment of the literature available on sub categories identified point out a possible solution by introducing the investment readiness levels, a diagnostic tool which represent the start-up's readiness for Angels and Venture Capitalist involvement and financial support. This metrics also facilitates a start-up rating system based on evidence on the progress of a start-up by milestones; which would eliminate the risks for investors. This finding suggests a considerable direction for future research.

Unclear Boundaries: Build-Measure Learn Process and the Point of Scaling in Applying the LSM Approach

The third objective of this study is to confirm the boundaries related to the LSM framework in terms of the build measure and learning process, and the starting point of scaling in practical application of the concept.

The lean approach is criticised for the lack of clarity in relation to the build-measure-learn process, which is one of the main principles of the theory. Blomberg (2012) and Kortman (2013) argue that contrary to the lean concept aims to eliminate external uncertainties, its results internal uncertainty. This internal uncertainty relates to the lack of clarity in terms of tests and feedbacks. Empirical evidence suggests that there is no linear relationship can be drawn between the number of validated hypotheses BLM process and the success of the teams utilising lean methods. (Ladd, 2016) Further problem linked to the practical application of the BLM process is that due to the fact that the lean start-up methodology does not provide a practical and clear rule for enough feedback (Blomberg, 2012)

Table 7:1: Lean Start-up Issues linked to the Build-Measure-Learn Process

Themes related to the BLM Process and Scaling Considerations			
Categories/Themes	Sub categories	No. of Responses	Frequency
Understanding the BML concept	<i>BML problems due to lack of understanding</i>	10	83.3%
	<i>BML issues linked to MVP confusion</i>	9	75%
	<i>BML for experimentation</i>	7	58.3%
	<i>BML for validation</i>	7	58.3%
Reverse BML	<i>Reverse BML Loop</i>	8	66%
	<i>Test before build</i>	5	41.6%
	<i>Determine the metrics before experiment</i>	5	41.6%
	<i>Turn uncertainty to knowledge</i>	2	16.6%
Importance of time in BML Process	<i>Dangers of quick validation</i>	2	16.6%
	<i>Dangers of early pivot</i>	2	16.6%
	<i>False negatives</i>	4	33.3%
	<i>Minimum time through the BML Loop</i>	7	58.3%
	<i>Accelerate the BML Loop</i>	10	83.3%
	<i>Focus on BML cycle time</i>	5	41.6%
Determination of the measure of progress in BLM	<i>Lean Analytics</i>	2	16.6%
	<i>Scaling depends on the viability of the business model</i>	6	50%
	<i>Scaling: what to measure</i>	3	25%
	<i>Scaling: how to measure</i>	3	25%

Table 7:2: Lean Start-up Issues linked to the Build-Measure-Learn Process-Frequency of Key Themes

Table 7 presents the sub categories and main themes emerged from the interviews discussing the issues identified from the literature review in relation to the BML process.

The most frequent theme identified relates to the interviews opinion that the inadequate understanding the BML concept results the internal uncertainty in the practical application of the approach.

“There is not a one size fits all rulebook on how to approach the build measure and learn process, similarly to the minimum viable product. The full understanding of the core concept will help you to define the settings of your experiment by which you implement the build measure feedback loop.” (Respondent 5- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

“BML refers to an experiment which assist the progress of the validated learning. One must clarify the appropriate context of the experiment: what they want to test, how they want to test and which parameters accepted for verification of the results.” (Respondent 8- Software Development, 1+ years of experience)

From the interviews it appears to be the most important thing to determine the concrete settings of the experiment by which the initial assumption of the product or a certain feature of the product will be tested and validated. Deciding on the settings of the experiment in terms of establishing key measurements for validation would reduce the uncertainty which linked to the implementation of the BML process.

Second most relevant theme identified related to the notion that the build measure learn loop should be reversed, as according to the lean approach the minimisation of resource use should be in the focus. By gathering information and validating the assumption on which the BLM experiment is based would certainly eliminate unnecessary resource utilisation. This finding refers to the appropriate design of the details of the experiment.

“The BLM cycle should be considered in reverse to learn-measure-build. Learning relates to understanding why you build measure refers to how you build and the build element refers to what to build.” (Respondent 7- Software Development, 1+ years of experience)

“I think that your initial assumption on which you develop your actual hypothesis should be also verified by a preliminary research and validation.” (Respondent 4- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

“There is already loads of information which you can find about your customers and their needs so it’s advisable to learn about them before you start to build your MVP. This saves you a lot of time and effort and ensures the effectiveness of the BML process.” (Respondent 1- Business Consultancy, 10+ years of experience)

The interviewees emphasised the importance of establishing metrics for the implementation of the build measure learn process, such metrics ought to be based on customer feedback or preliminary market research. This enables to determine the measurement of the results in a more appropriate way, based on actual knowledge on the market.

Third theme emerged from the interviews suggest the importance of time in the Build- Measure-Learn process. As the core tenant of the lean start-up methodology is to eliminate wastage, the focus should be on the acceleration of the BML cycle, thus achieve time effectiveness.

“Speed is considered as a critical ingredient to the lean approach, the quicker you facilitate the build measure learn cycle and learn from the results the quicker you can facilitate another experiment based on the knowledge from the previous cycle and get one step closer to success.” (Respondent 1- Business Consultancy, 10+ years of experience)

“Even Ries emphasises the importance of speed in the build measure learn cycle, I think one of the most important lean principle is the focus on cycle time. The quicker the cycle the more cost and time effective the learning is.” (Respondent 6-Cathering Industry, 5 years of experience)

“Appropriate timing is very important in the build measure learn cycle: the aim is to learn as quickly as possible to decide on preserving or pivot” (Respondent 11- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

From the opinions of the interviewees, it seems that appropriate timing facilitates quicker validation of the initial hypothesis and learning about the market or results a quicker pivot, a correction of course. Speed in the BML determines the effectiveness and enables the quicker iteration of the process. Ries (2011) emphasizes fast iteration in the BML process cycle with the goal of maximise the learning of each cycle in the minimum amount of time.

The last important theme identified according to the sub-categories emerged from the discussions is the relevance of the determination of progress measurements.

According to the interviewees the previous identification of the key measurements to which the results of the experiment is compared against is vital in the BML process.

“You have to decide on the implications that data has on your hypothesis, therefore you must identify the most important, actionable metrics and the acceptable results according to these metrics to achieve the goal of validated learning. Such results also indicate your progress for yourself and for possible investors.” (Respondent 11- Start-up Consultancy, 7+ years of experience)

“In simple terms key metrics refers to the identification of what to measure and how the measure and what are the results which defines the next step. The topic of lean analytics provides a practical guidance how to apply metrics in lean start-up development.” (Respondent 8- Software Development, 1+ years of experience).

The interviewees discussing the issues related to scaling agreed on the importance of metrics for the determination of the appropriate measurements to which the start-ups

progress is compared to. These measurements hold the entrepreneurs accountable for progress. Validation of the business model should be based on appropriate metrics which enable evidence-based business decisions and signals the viability of the business model. As this viability has been proven entrepreneurs are able to scale their start-ups. Scaling point of the business is determined by the validation of all assumptions and hypotheses by actionable metrics articulated in the business model canvas. Angel investment can be sought as the viability is proven by the appropriate metrics.

The findings correspond with the additional literature search as according to (Blank, 2012) the goal of the BLM is to maximise learning. The unit of progress is the validated learning which suggests a rigorous method for demonstrating the progress. The acceleration of the BML cycle results faster learning. According to Ferres (2017) to monitor and evaluate a start-up the progress ought to be measured. Actionable metrics and the innovation accounting proposed by Ries (2011) enables progress monitoring and quick adjustments based on quantifiable evidence. Ultimately it determines whether the entrepreneur is persevering or pivot from the actual hypothesis.

To conclude the third area of discussions the understanding and determination of appropriate measurements to which the progress is compared facilitate evidence based validation. However, it seems there are considerable drawbacks of the high emphasis on quick validation.

Additional Areas of Considerations

The interviews revealed further considerable areas in relation to the LSM concept which are not linked directly to the critical areas identified from the literature, but seems to have high importance in the practical implementation of the lean framework. These areas are outside the barriers of this study, however propose opportunities for future research.

Table 8: Additional Areas of Considerations Emerged from the Analysis

Additional Areas of Considerations			
Categories/Themes	Sub categories	No. of Responses	Frequency
Possible Solution for funding issues	<i>Lean funding</i>	6	50%
	<i>Growth hacking</i>	5	41.6%
Concepts built upon the LSM	<i>Lean analytics</i>	3	25%
	<i>Lean canvas</i>	2	16.6%
	<i>Actionable metrics</i>	4	33.3%
Scaling of the business	<i>Engines of growth</i>	7	58.3%

The first theme offers possible solution for the funding issues apart from bootstrapping and crowdfunding established previously: the lean funding. The conceptual basis of lean funding assumes the investors understanding of the concept and the connection between the LSM and the funding cycle (Dowling, 2015)

The second theme emerged from the discussions related to the various concepts built upon the principles of the lean start-up methodology. Growth hacking is the lean approach applied to marketing: a data and product driven experiment based marketing approach. (Ellis, 2016) Lean analytics further develop the actionable metrics of the LSM (Croll and Yoskovitz, 2013). while the lean canvas offers an appropriate tool for the LSM (Maurya, 2016).

Conclusions

To conclude the findings by answering the research question that the critical success factors of implementing the LSM for new venture creation can be validated by practical experience based on the research objectives achieved:

In the practical application of the concept the most relevant critical factor as per the academic literature linked to the Minimum Viable Product element of the framework. Critics state that the most relevant limitation of the LSM approach in practice is the confusion related to the MVP and the concerns of quality. (Nirwan and Dhewanto, 2014; Heitmann, 2014 and Hussein, 2015)

The findings developed on the basis of expert opinions identified that the mentioned criticism is caused by the inadequate level of understanding the MVP concept and implementation in practice. The MVP is a strategic process by which entrepreneurs are able to facilitate learning in a cost effective way, with the minimisation of the resources. Therefore, the MVP is not necessarily a physical product, it can be any hypothesis related experiment on the product or the business model, which is based on an initial assumption. This MVP is created to be tested and validated on actual the market. The determinants of viability are product and market specific. The analysis also revealed the importance of engaging early adopters. The development of an early audience would eliminate the quality concerns related to the concept.

Other considerable criticism related to the funding associated issues in the implementation process of the lean start-up methodology. (Pelling, 2015; Walton; 2015 and Rowen, 2017)

The findings show that new venture funding is based on the stages of development. The initial funding options available for start-ups are bootstrapping and

crowdfunding. The lean start-up methodology proposes a concept by which the prestart up phase funding requirements can be minimised, and recommend an approach by which the viability of the product or business model can be validated with the least resource need. In addition, the findings suggest an evidence based measuring system (Investment Readiness Levels) to highlight the progress of the start-up, which could form the basis of the evaluation of external investors and would be suitable to communicate the business idea with potential investors.

The criticism proposed by Kortman (2013) and Ladd (2016) in terms of the uncertainty related to the build-measure-learn process and the linked starting point of scaling formed the third research objective. In relation to the uncertainty of the BML process it can be stated that similarly to the minimum viable product concept the understanding of the build measure learn approach is important in the practical application. The key tenant of the LSM is to accelerate the learning process and to provide evidence based on predetermined metrics of the learning process. By speeding up the process the method eliminates wasted time and resources. Important finding which seems to contradict the original framework is that most of the expert suggested that the build-measure-learn cycle implies a backwards cycle as well; the initial assumptions should be based on preliminary market test and customer feedbacks.

The scaling point of the business is determined by the validation of all assumptions and hypotheses articulated in the business model canvas by the iterative BML cycles thus prove the viability of the new venture. This scaling point coincides the point of product market fit in the customer development concept by Blank (2012)

Academic Relevance

This study provides empiric evidence based on the assessment of the practical implementation of the lean start-up framework. Additionally, the findings may form an empirical support for the lean start-up methodology thus contribute to the theoretical debate on the subject. However, traditional business planning approach may be applicable for larger companies executing strategic plans based on known market conditions, for new venture development the implication of the lean approach seems to be more effective due to the series of uncertainty in terms of product and market.

According to the findings of this study the lean start-up methodology provides a solution to the problem statement related to high start-up failure rates. By adopting the lean principles and find the product market fit point through the process of the iterative build measure learn cycles entrepreneurs will be able to increase the chances of their success. Advocating the use of lean methods of new venture development would result lower failure rate than the traditional business planning methods.

The findings seem to confirm the viability of a new academic domain which based on scientific methods adopted from software development would be applicable in the area of new venture development.

Practical Implications of the Findings

The lean start-up methodology proposes a new approach for entrepreneurs to build successful businesses. The lean approach provides a workable concept for creating a new business venture and significantly increase the chances of success, by systematically and gradually eliminating the risks of the initial assumptions of the business idea related to the product and the market. The application of lean principles enables entrepreneurs to verify the validity of their business idea based on factual evidence from the market also provide evidence-based evaluation for investors facilitate the early stage funding. Contrary to the traditional business planning approach the lean start-up methodology result resource efficiency and minimises the risks of failure.

Limitations and Recommended Areas for Future Research

Limitations of this research relate to the implemented qualitative approach for theory development, the abductive reasoning, the sampling method and the data collection and analysis process. The concerns of credibility, reliability and validity as well as the issues related to personal biases must be addressed.

As per Silverman (2010) and Rahman (2016) limitations associated with a qualitative research strategy relate to the lower credibility of results from qualitative approach due to the focus on experiences. The smaller sample size raises issues in relation to generalisability, and the data analysis and interpretation may be more complex, difficult and takes a considerable amount of time. (Flick, 2011; Thompson, 2011 and Berg and Lune, 2012). Challenges associated with the use of e-mail interviewing in qualitative research as per Meho (2006) related to the requirement that the questions ought to be self-explanatory, the answers are affected by the respondent's interpretation. Furthermore, considerable drawback of this method linked to the increased time for getting response.

Credibility of research findings with regards to the research design utilised for conducting the study, depends on the reliability, validity and generalisability which imposes further limitation to this study.

Reliability relates to the question of consistent research findings, which concerns the replicability of the research in other settings and yielding the same results. (Easterby-Smith et al., 2012) the reliability improved by emphasis on data saturation' and consistency in the interviews provided by the semi-structured interviewing which involves posing similar questions to each interviewee.

Validity concerns relates to ensuring credibility. The validity of this study is improved by the implementation of a structured interview schedule to provide guidance for the interview process. Generalisability issues related to the research design implemented.

Personal biases also raise significant limitation to this study, interpretivism due to its subjective nature is impacted by biases both from the researcher and the participants. The subjectivity of the opinions and personal experiences also imposes limitations in terms of reliability. Result verification similarly considered as a limitation to qualitative studies. (Saunders et al. 2014).

Further limitation of this research is the time constraint which restricts the amount of data collected.

The additional areas of investigations emerged from the analysis of the interviews are presented by Table 8. These suggest possible areas for further investigations which are outside the boundaries of this research. The assessment of lean funding would be a considerable area for future research as this study concluded debatable findings in relation to it. Further considerable areas for future research may be based on the themes of Lean Canvas, Lean Analytics and Growth Hacking for marketing.

Future empiric studies may consider to undertake a quantitative research and by providing evidence based on statistical analysis contribute to the field of the LSM.

The author considers to undertake a longitudinal- action research by applying the lean principles to his recent start-up development.

References

- Alvarez, S.A. and Barney, J.B. (2007). The entrepreneurial theory of the firm. *Journal of Management Studies*, 44(7), pp.1057-1063.
- Arkenas, R. and Finn, P. (2016). The Go-to-Market Approach Start-ups Need to Adopt. [Online] *Harvard Business Review*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2016/06/the-go-to-market-approach-startups-need-to-adopt> [Accessed 1 Sep. 2017].
- Atkinson, R. and Flint, J., (2001). Accessing hidden and hard-to-reach populations: Snowball research strategies. *Social research update*, 33(1), pp.1-4.
- Audretsch, D.B., (2002). The dynamic role of small firms: Evidence from the US. *Small Business Economics*, 18(1), pp.13-40.
- Bajpai, N. (2011) *Business Research Methods* Pearson Education India
- Bampton, R. and Cowton, C.J., (2002) the e-interview. In *Qualitative Social Research* (Vol. 3, No. 2).
- Bell D. (1974) *Coming of Post-Industrial Society*. London: Heinemann.
- Birch, M. and Miller, T. (2002). Encouraging participation: ethics and responsibilities. *Ethics in qualitative research*, pp.91-106.
- Black, I. (2006). The presentation of interpretivist research. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 9(4), 319–324
- Blank, S. (2013). Why the Lean Start-Up Changes Everything. [Online] *Harvard Business Review*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2013/05/why-the-lean-start-up-changes-everything> [Accessed 5 Feb. 2017].
- Blank, S. (2015). Why ‘Build, Measure, Learn’ isn’t just throwing things against the wall to see if they work. [Online] Available at: <https://medium.com/startup-grind/why-build-measure-learn-isn-t-just-throwing-things-against-the-wall-to-see-if-they-work-dccc75092f6b> [Accessed 16 Feb. 2017].
- Blank, S. and Dorf, B., (2012). *The Start-up Owner's Manual*. Pescadero, CA: K&S Ranch.
- Blank, S., (2011). Embrace failure to start up success. *Nature News*, 477(7363), pp.133-133.
- Blomberg, A., (2012). *The Lean Start-up Approach—and its applicability outside Silicon Valley* (Doctoral dissertation, Master’s thesis).
- Bocken, N.M.P., Short, S.W., Rana, P. and Evans, S., (2014). A literature and practice review to develop sustainable business model archetypes. *Journal of cleaner production*, 65, pp.42-56.

- Boyce, C. and Neale, P., (2006). *Conducting in-depth interviews: A guide for designing and conducting in-depth interviews for evaluation input*
- Bryman A. & Bell, E. (2015) *Business Research Methods* 4th edition, Oxford University Press
- Bryman, A., (2006). Integrating quantitative and qualitative research: how is it done?. *Qualitative research*, 6(1), pp.97-113.
- Bull, I. and Willard, G.E., (1993). Towards a theory of entrepreneurship. *Journal of business venturing*, 8(3), pp.183-195.
- Burgstone J. (2012). What's Wrong With the Lean Start-up? [Online] Available at: <https://www.inc.com/jon-burgstone/flaws-in-the-lean-start-up.html> [Accessed 5 Apr. 2017].
- Campbell, D.F. and Carayannis, E.G., (2016). The academic firm: a new design and redesign proposition for entrepreneurship in innovation-driven knowledge economy. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 5(1), p.12.
- Carson, D., Gilmore, A., Perry, C., and Gronhaug, K. (2001). *Qualitative Marketing Research*. London: Sage.
- Caruso, L., (2016). The knowledge-based economy and the relationship between the economy and society in contemporary capitalism. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 19(3), pp.409-430.
- Cassell, C. and Symon, G. (2004). *Essential guide to qualitative methods in organizational research*. Sage.
- Charmaz, K., (2007). Constructionism and the grounded theory method. *Handbook of constructionist research*, 1, pp.397-412.
- Coomber, R., (1997). *Using the Internet for survey research*.
- Croll, A. and Yoskovitz, B., (2013). *Lean analytics: Use data to build a better start-up faster*. "O'Reilly Media, Inc."
- De Wet, M., (2013). *Lean Startup methodology: An exploratory study of the principles applied by South African e-retailers*.
- Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S., (2002). *The qualitative inquiry reader*. Sage.
- Dowling, P. (2015). *Lean Funding for Start-ups*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.dreamstake.net/blog/lean-funding-for-startups/> [Accessed 19 Jul. 2017].
- Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Jackson, P. (2012) *Management Research*. London: Sage Publication
- Eisenmann, T.R., Ries, E. and Dillard, S., (2012). *Hypothesis-driven entrepreneurship: The lean start-up*.

- Furr, N. and Ahlstrom, P., (2011). Nail it then scale it: the entrepreneur's guide to creating and managing breakthrough innovation (No. 658.421 FUR. CIMMYT.).
- Gartner, W.B., (1985). A conceptual framework for describing the phenomenon of new venture creation. *Academy of management review*, 10(4), pp.696-706.
- George, G. and Bock, A.J., (2011). The business model in practice and its implications for entrepreneurship research. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 35(1), pp.83-111.
- Gruber (2007)
- Ghorashi, H., (2015). Challenges of the Lean Startup Method: Entrepreneurial Knowledge Management during the BML-Loop (Bachelor's thesis, University of Twente).
- Hallebone, E. and Priest, J., (2009). Chapter 4: Philosophies of Science: The bedrock of good research. *Business and Management research: Paradigms and Practices*, pp.45-70.
- Heitmann, J., (2014). The Lean Start-up-A pragmatic view on its Flaws and Pitfalls (Bachelor's thesis, University of Twente).
- Hindle, K. and Klyver, K. (2011). *Handbook of research on new venture creation*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Howe, J., (2006). Crowdsourcing: A definition. *Crowdsourcing: Tracking the rise of the amateur*.
- Hussein, N. (2017). What's wrong with the lean start-up methodology? [Online] The Next Web. Available at: https://thenextweb.com/entrepreneur/2015/07/05/whats-wrong-with-the-lean-startup-methodology/#.tnw_g53JAVz7 [Accessed 15 Feb. 2017].
- Kaltenecker, N., Hoerndlein, C. and Hess, T., (2013) The Importance of the Business Idea for New Venture Creation in the Software Industry. In *International Conference of Software Business* (pp. 153-165). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg
- Katz, J. A. (1990) longitudinal analysis of self-employment follow-through. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, Vol. 2, No: 1, 15–25
- Katz, J. and Gartner, W.B., (1988). Properties of emerging organizations. *Academy of management review*, 13(3), pp.429-441.
- Kilkku, V. (2017). Lean Start-up's Build-Measure-Learn loop and the PDSA cycle. [Online] Kilkku.com. Available at: <http://www.kilkku.com/blog/2014/05/lean-startups-build-measure-learn-loop-and-the-pdsa-cycle/> [Accessed 8 Aug. 2017].
- Kolbe, R.H. and Burnett, M.S., (1991). Content-analysis research: An examination of applications with directives for improving research reliability and objectivity. *Journal of consumer research*, 18(2), pp.243-250.

- Kortman, P. (2013). The problem with a Lean Start-up: the Minimum Viable Product. - Paul Kortman. [Online] Paul Kortman. Available at: <http://paulkortman.com/2012/11/21/the-problem-with-a-lean-startup-the-minimum-viable-product/> [Accessed 6 Apr. 2017].
- Kritikos, A.S., (2014). Entrepreneurs and their impact on jobs and economic growth. IZA World of Labor
- Krueger, N., (1993). The impact of prior entrepreneurial exposure on perceptions of new venture feasibility and desirability. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and practice*, 18(1), pp.5-22.
- Ladd, T. (2016). The Limits of the Lean Start-up Method. [Online] Harvard Business Review. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2016/03/the-limits-of-the-lean-startup-method> [Accessed 11 May 2017].
- Lai, W.H. and Lin, C.C., (2015). Constructing business incubation service capabilities for tenants at post-entrepreneurial phase. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(11), pp.2285-2289.
- Lazear, E.P., (2004). Balanced skills and entrepreneurship. *The American Economic Review*, 94(2), pp.208-211.
- Mankins, J.C., (1995). Technology readiness levels. White Paper, April, 6.
- Maritz, A. and Donovan, J., (2015). Entrepreneurship and innovation: Setting an agenda for greater discipline contextualisation. *Education+ Training*, 57(1), pp.74-87
- Marshall, C. and Rossman, G., (2006). The how of the study: Building the research design. *Designing qualitative research*, pp.55-101.
- McGrath, R.G., MacMillan, I.C. and Venkataraman, S., (1995). Defining and developing competence: A strategic process paradigm. *Strategic management journal*, 16(4), pp.251-275.
- Meho, L.I., (2006). E-mail interviewing in qualitative research: A methodological discussion. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 57(10), pp.1284-1295.
- Meyer, K.E. and Peng, M.W., (2016). Theoretical foundations of emerging economy business research. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 47(1), pp.3-22.
- Morris, M., Schindehutte, M. and Allen, J., (2005). The entrepreneur's business model: toward a unified perspective. *Journal of business research*, 58(6), pp.726-735.
- Myers, M.D. (2008) "Qualitative Research in Business & Management" SAGE Publications

- Nirwan, M.D., & Dhewanto, W. (2014). Barriers in implementing the lean startup methodology in Indonesia – case study of B2B start-up. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 169, 23-30.
- Nobel, C., (2011). *Teaching a Lean Startup Strategy*. HBS Working Knowledge, pp.1-2.
- Noy, C., (2008). Sampling knowledge: The hermeneutics of snowball sampling in qualitative research. *International Journal of social research methodology*, 11(4), pp.327-344.
- O'donoghue, T., (2006). *Planning your qualitative research project: An introduction to interpretivist research in education*. Routledge.
- Ohno, T., (1988). *Toyota production system: beyond large-scale production*. crc Press.
- Olsen, W., (2004). Triangulation in social research: Qualitative and quantitative methods can really be mixed. *Developments in sociology*, 20, pp.103-118.
- Osterwalder, A. and Pigneur, Y., (2010). *Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Pelling, N. (2015). Lean Start-ups suck. Here are 10 reasons why.... [Online] *Funding Start-ups (& other impossibilities)*. Available at: <https://nanodome.wordpress.com/2011/10/05/lean-startups-suck-here-are-10-reasons-why/> [Accessed 5 Apr. 2017].
- Qvillberg, J. and Gustafsson, A., (2012). *Implementing lean startup methodology- An evaluation*.
- Reichertz, J., (2007). *Abduction: The logic of discovery of grounded theory* (pp. 214-228). London: Sage.
- Reynolds, P.D. and White, S.B., (1997). *The entrepreneurial process: Economic growth, men, women, and minorities*. Praeger Pub Text.
- Ries, E., (2011). *The lean startup: How today's entrepreneurs use continuous innovation to create radically successful businesses*. Crown Business.
- Rowen, A. (2017). What's happening in start-up funding? | Cognite Ventures. [online] *Cogniteventures.com*. Available at: <http://www.cogniteventures.com/2017/03/28/whats-happening-in-startup-funding/> [Accessed 6 Apr. 2017].
- Salamzadeh, A. and Kawamorita Kesim, H., (2015). *Start-up Companies: Life Cycle and Challenges*
- Salas Martinez, M., (2016). *Good Practices of the Lean Start-up Methodology: Benefits, challenges and recommendations*.

- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2014) "Research Methods for Business Students" 6th edition, Pearson Education Limited
- Schendel, D. and Hofer, C.W. eds., 1979. Strategic management: A new view of business policy and planning. Little, Brown.
- Start-up Genome Project (2017). Start-up Genome – The Global Start up Ecosystem Report 2017. [Online] Available at: <https://startupgenome.com> [Accessed 9 Apr. 2017].
- Svennevig, J., 2001. Abduction as a methodological approach to the study of spoken interaction. *Norskraft*, 103, pp.1-22.
- Tan, W.L. (2003). Entrepreneurship and Innovation in the Knowledge-based Economy: Challenges and strategies. Asian Productivity Organization.
- Thiel, P. (2017). [Online] Available at: <https://genius.com/Peter-thiel-lecture-5-business-strategy-and-monopoly-theory-annotated> [Accessed 8 May 2017].
- Thurik, R. and Wennekers, S., (2004). Entrepreneurship, small business and economic growth. *Journal of small business and enterprise development*, 11(1), pp.140-149.
- Tkachev, A. and Kolvereid, L., (1999). Self-employment intentions among Russian students. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 11(3), pp.269-280.
- Valliere, D., and R. Peterson. (2008) "Entrepreneurship and economic growth: Evidence from emerging and developed countries." *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development* 21:5–6 (2009): 459–480.
- Van de Ven, A.H., Hudson, R. and Schroeder, D.M., (1984). Designing new business startups: Entrepreneurial, organizational, and ecological considerations. *Journal of management*, 10(1), pp.87-108.
- Walton, H. (2015). Lean Start-Up, and How It Almost Killed Our Company. [online] Available at: <https://www.infoq.com/articles/lean-startup-killed> [Accessed 4 Apr. 2017].
- Wong, P.K., Ho, Y.P. and Autio, E., (2005). Entrepreneurship, innovation and economic growth: Evidence from GEM data. *Small business economics*, 24(3), pp.335-350.
- Zott, C., Amit, R. and Massa, L., 2011. The business model: recent developments and future research. *Journal of management*, 37(4), pp.1019-1042.